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**PREVALENCE OF GASTROESOPHAGEAL
REFLUX DISEASE AMONG PATIENTS
PRESENTING IN EMERGENCY
DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT:

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), is a chronic condition in which stomach contents rise into the esophagus, resulting in symptoms and/or complications. Symptoms include the taste of acid in the back of the mouth, heartburn, bad breath, chest pain, regurgitation, breathing problems, and wearing away of the teeth. Complications include esophagitis, esophageal stricture, and Barrett's esophagus. Risk factors include obesity, pregnancy, smoking, hiatal hernia, and taking certain medicines. This study was conducted among the patients presenting in the emergency department with stomachache or heartburn. Name, age, gender, presence of GERD and history and duration of symptoms were noted on a predefined proforma. A total of 132 patients were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 41.23 ± 6.71 years. There were 20 males and 34 females. A total of 54 patients were suffering from GERD. There were 20 (37%) males and 34 (63%) females presented with upper respiratory tract infections.

Keyword: Gastroesophageal reflux disease

INTRODUCTION:

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), is a chronic condition in which stomach contents rise into the esophagus, resulting in symptoms and/or complications. Symptoms include the taste of acid in the back of the mouth, heartburn, bad breath, chest pain, regurgitation, breathing problems, and wearing away of the teeth. Complications include esophagitis, esophageal stricture, and Barrett's esophagus. Risk factors include obesity, pregnancy, smoking, hiatal hernia, and taking certain medicines. Medications that may cause or worsen the disease include benzodiazepines, calcium channel blockers, tricyclic antidepressants, NSAIDs, certain asthma medicine. Acid reflux is due to poor closure of the lower esophageal sphincter, which is at the junction between the stomach and the esophagus. Diagnosis among those who do not improve with simpler measures may involve gastroscopy, upper GI series, esophageal pH monitoring, or esophageal manometry.

Treatment options include lifestyle changes, medications, and sometimes surgery for those who do not improve with the first two measures. Lifestyle changes include not lying down for three hours after eating, lying down on the left side, raising the pillow/bedhead height, losing weight, avoiding foods which result in symptoms, and stopping smoking. Medications include antacids, H₂ receptor blockers, proton pump inhibitors, and prokinetics. In the Western world, between 10 and 20% of the population is affected by GERD. Occasional gastroesophageal reflux without troublesome symptoms or complications is even more common. The classic symptoms of GERD were first described in 1925, when Friedenwald and Feldman commented on heartburn and its possible relationship to a hiatal hernia. In 1934 gastroenterologist Asher Winkelstein described reflux and attributed the symptoms to stomach acid. GERD may lead to Barrett's esophagus, a type of intestinal metaplasia, which is in turn a precursor condition for esophageal cancer. The risk of progression from Barrett's to dysplasia is uncertain but is estimated at about 20% of cases. Due to the risk of chronic heartburn progressing to Barrett's, EGD every five years is recommended for people with

chronic heartburn, or who take drugs for chronic GERD (1-3). The objective of this study is to evaluate the prevalence of gastroesophageal reflux disease among patients presenting in emergency department.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study was conducted among the patients presenting in the emergency department with stomachache or heartburn. Name, age, gender, presence of GERD and history and duration of symptoms were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 26.0. The quantitative variables, i.e., age, duration of infection was presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables, i.e., gender, the presence of GERD was presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 132 patients were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 41.23 ± 6.71 years. There were 20 males and 34 females. A total of 54 patients were suffering from GERD. There were 20 (37%) males and 34 (63%) females presented with upper respiratory tract infections.

DISCUSSION:

The treatments for GERD may include food choices, lifestyle changes, medications, and possibly surgery. Initial treatment is frequently with a proton-pump inhibitor such as omeprazole. In some cases, a person with GERD symptoms can manage them by taking over-the-counter drugs. This is often safer and less expensive than taking prescription drugs. Some guidelines recommend trying to treat symptoms with an H2 antagonist before using a proton-pump inhibitor because of cost and safety concerns. Certain foods may promote GERD, but most dietary interventions have little effect. Some evidence suggests that reduced sugar intake and increased fiber intake can help. Avoidance of specific foods and not eating before lying down are recommended for those having GERD symptoms. Foods that may precipitate

GERD include coffee, alcohol, chocolate, fatty foods, acidic foods, and spicy foods.

Weight loss may be effective in reducing the severity and frequency of symptoms. Elevating the head of the entire bed with blocks, or using a wedge pillow that elevates the individual's shoulders and head, may inhibit GERD when lying down. Although moderate exercise may improve symptoms in people with GERD, vigorous exercise may worsen them. Breathing exercises may relieve GERD symptoms. Abstinence from smoking or alcohol does not appear to significantly relieve symptoms. The standard surgical treatment for severe GERD is the Nissen fundoplication. In this procedure, the upper part of the stomach is wrapped around the lower esophageal sphincter to strengthen the sphincter and prevent acid reflux and to repair a hiatal hernia. It is recommended only for those who do not improve with PPIs. Quality of life is improved in the short term compared to medical therapy, but there is uncertainty in the benefits over surgery versus long-term medical management with proton pump inhibitors. When comparing different fundoplication techniques, partial posterior fundoplication surgery is more effective than partial anterior fundoplication surgery, and partial fundoplication has better outcomes than total fundoplication. Esophagogastric dissociation is an alternative procedure that is sometimes used to treat neurologically impaired children with GERD. Preliminary studies have shown it may have a lower failure rate and a lower incidence of recurrent reflux (4-6).

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